

СРАВНЕНИЕ СЕМЕЙСТВА АЛГОРИТМОВ SHA

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Аннотация: Семейство алгоритмов SHA представляет собой набор криптографических функций хеширования, широко используемых для защиты данных и аутентификации. В статье рассматриваются типы алгоритмов SHA, их архитектура и уровни безопасности. Анализируются уязвимости SHA-1 перед современными угрозами, эффективность и надежность семейства SHA-2, а также инновационная архитектура и устойчивость семейства SHA-3. Обсуждаются преимущества и недостатки каждого алгоритма, а также области их применения. Статья направлена на освещение эволюции алгоритмов SHA и их практической значимости.

Ключевые слова: Алгоритмы SHA, криптографическое хеширование, SHA-1, SHA-2, SHA-3, уровень безопасности, коллизия, эффективность, криптографическая безопасность, защита данных, алгоритм, реализация, хеш-функция.

Annotatsiya: SHA algoritmlar oilasi – bu kriptografik xeshlash funksiyalari to‘plami bo‘lib, ma‘lumotlarni himoya qilish va autentifikatsiya qilishda keng qo‘llaniladi. Maqolada SHA algoritmlarining turlari, ularning arxitekturasi va xavfsizlik darajalari tahlil qilindi. SHA-1 algoritmining zamonaviy tahdidlarga qarshi zaifligi, SHA-2 oilasining samaradorligi va xavfsizlik darajasi, shuningdek, SHA-3 algoritmlar oilasining innovatsion arxitekturasi va mukammalligi tasniflandi. Har bir algoritmning afzallik va kamchiliklari, shuningdek, ularning qo‘llanilish sohalari yoritib berildi. Maqola SHA algoritmlarining rivojlanishi va ularning amaliy ahamiyatini ochib berishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: SHA algoritmlari, kriptografik xeshlash, SHA-1, SHA-2, SHA-3, xavfsizlik darajasi, kolliziya, samaradorlik, kriptografik xavfsizlik, ma‘lumotlarni himoya qilish, algoritm, realizatsiya qilish, xesh funksiya.

Abstract: The SHA algorithm family is a set of cryptographic hashing functions widely used for data protection and authentication. The article examines the types of SHA algorithms, their architecture, and security levels. It classifies the vulnerabilities of SHA-1 against modern threats, the efficiency and security of the SHA-2 family, as well as the innovative architecture and robustness of the SHA-3 family. The advantages and disadvantages of each algorithm, along with their application areas,

are discussed. The article aims to highlight the evolution of SHA algorithms and their practical significance.

Key words: SHA algorithms, cryptographic hashing, SHA-1, SHA-2, SHA-3, security level, collision, efficiency, cryptographic security, data protection, algorithm, implementation, hash function.

Introduction. SHA (Secure Hash Algorithm) algorithms represent an important family of cryptographic hashing functions and are widely used for securing data, authentication, and detecting errors or alterations. These algorithms are essential tools in ensuring data integrity and play a key role in security systems. The various versions of SHA, namely SHA-1, SHA-2, and SHA-3, differ in terms of security levels, efficiency, and architecture. This article analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of these algorithms through comparative analysis and evaluates their compliance with modern security requirements. The unique features and application areas of each algorithm are highlighted, with a detailed examination of their differences and development processes. The implementation of the hashing process within the SHA algorithm family was realized, and comparative analysis involved the following methods:

Literature Analysis: Scientific literature and technical documents relevant to the topic were studied.

Experimental Method: The performance, security level, and processing speed of each SHA algorithm were compared through experiments.

Analytical Method: Theoretical analysis was conducted to evaluate differences between algorithms, their strengths and weaknesses, and the likelihood of generating collisions.

Analysis

SHA-0 is a cryptographic hash function developed by NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) in 1993^[1]. It is designed to generate a fixed-size hash value from an arbitrary-length input. Specifically, it produces a 160-bit hash value that can be used to secure large amounts of data.

SHA-1 (Secure Hash Algorithm 1) was introduced by NIST in 1995 as an improved version of SHA-0, addressing its vulnerabilities. SHA-1 generates a 160-bit hash value and was widely used for ensuring data security, particularly in creating digital signatures and certificates. However, despite its initial reliability, it was discovered in 2005 that SHA-1 is prone to collision attacks, significantly reducing its security. This prompted the development of new algorithms under the SHA-2 family.

The core principle of the algorithm is as follows: The input is an arbitrary-length message, with a maximum length of 2^{64} . The output is a fixed 160-bit (20-byte) hash value. Using specific algorithmic transformations, the input data is condensed into a 160-bit hash.

The working process of the algorithm can be broken down into the following steps:

1. *Padding the Message:* The total length of the message should be 512 bits. Convert the input message to binary and append a single bit "1" (00000001). Reserve the last 64 bits for the length of the original message in binary. Add zeros (00000000) after the "1" until the message length reaches 448 bits. Append the binary representation of the original message length at the end. If the length is not 64 bits, pad with additional zeros. The final message will be 512 bits long. This 512-bit block, composed of 0s and 1s, is written as 64×8 blocks.

2. From a 64×8 structure of 512 bits, we obtain 16 messages of 32 bits each: $word[i]$, where $0 \leq i \leq 15$. The message is then extended to 80 words of 32 bits by adding additional 32-bit words. To do so, the remaining $80 - 16 = 64$ 32-bit words are generated using the following sequence of operations and appended to the message. The extended sequence of 64 additional 32-bit words is formed as follows:

$word[i]$, where $16 \leq i \leq 79$.

$$word[i] = (word[i - 3] \wedge word[i - 8] \wedge word[i - 14] \wedge word[i - 16]) \ll 1$$

3. In the next step, 5 variables are selected as constants. This process ensures the implementation of iterative progress:

$$h0 = 0x67452301 = a$$

$$h3 = 0x10325476 = d$$

$$h1 = 0xEFCDAB89 = b$$

$$h4 = 0xC3D2E1F0 = e$$

$$h2 = 0x98BADCFE = c$$

4. The SHA-1 hashing algorithm uses 4 constant k values, which are applied to every 20 32-bit words. These constants are derived from the square roots of the numbers 2, 3, 5, and 10.

$$k1 = 0x5A827999$$

$$k3 = 0x8F1BBCDC$$

$$k2 = 0x6ED9EBA1$$

$$k4 = 0xCA62C1D6$$

$$0 \leq i \leq 19 \rightarrow k1$$

$$40 \leq i \leq 59 \rightarrow k3$$

$$20 \leq i \leq 39 \rightarrow k2$$

$$60 \leq i \leq 79 \rightarrow k4$$

5. The resulting 80 32-bit words are transformed through logical operations. This process consists of 4 stages, where each stage utilizes a specific sequence of logical operations for its respective 20 words. Each stage corresponds to one of the constants ($k1, k2, k3, k4$), and at each stage, the

variables resulting from the logical operations of the previous stage (h_0, h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4) are used.

If $0 \leq i \leq 19$, $f = (b \wedge c) \vee (\neg b \wedge d)$, k_1 .

If $20 \leq i \leq 39$, $f = b \wedge c \wedge d$, k_2 .

If $40 \leq i \leq 59$, $f = (b \wedge c) \vee (b \wedge d) \vee (c \wedge d)$, k_3 .

If $60 \leq i \leq 79$, $f = b \wedge c \wedge d$, k_4 .

$help = (a \ll 5) + f + e + k + word[i]$

$e = d$

$c = b \ll 30$

$d = c$

$b = a$

$a = help$

6. It should be noted that some of the expressions above can be replaced with their equivalent forms.

For example:

$0 \leq i \leq 19$ $f = d \wedge (b \wedge (c \wedge d))$

$0 \leq i \leq 19$ $f = (b \wedge c) \wedge (\neg b \wedge d)$

$0 \leq i \leq 19$ $f = (b \wedge c) + (\neg b \wedge d)$

$40 \leq i \leq 59$ $f = (b \wedge c) \vee (d \wedge (b \vee c))$

$40 \leq i \leq 59$ $f = (b \wedge c) \vee (d \wedge (b \wedge c))$

$40 \leq i \leq 59$ $f = (b \wedge c) + (d \wedge (b \wedge c))$

$40 \leq i \leq 59$ $f = (b \wedge c) \wedge (b \wedge d) \wedge (c \vee d)$

7. To obtain the final result, the 5 variables generated after the 80 iterations are added to the initially given 5 variables. Logical operations are then performed on the resulting 5 numbers, producing a 160-bit (20-byte) message as the output.

$h_0 = h_0 + a$

$h_2 = h_2 + c$

$h_1 = h_1 + b$

$h_3 = h_3 + d$

$h_4 = h_4 + e$

$h_{total} = (h_0 \ll 128) \vee (h_1 \ll 96) \vee (h_2 \ll 64) \vee (h_3 \ll 32) \vee h_4$

During the algorithm, 80 iterations of transformations are carried out using logical operations such as XOR, AND, OR, NOT, addition, and left-shift. As a result, a message of arbitrary length is converted into a 160-bit hash representation.

Implementation of the SHA-1 Algorithm in Python:

Since hashes are performed in the binary number system, a for loop operator is used to convert the message into binary.

for n in range(len(data)):

data_bit += '{0:08b}'.format(ord(data[n]))

A while loop operator is applied to pad the data to (448 mod 512) bits:

while len(data_binary) % 512 != 448:

data_binary += "0"

To create an array of n-bit values:

array_binary funksiyasi yaratiladi:

def array_binary(l, n):

return [l[i:i+n] for i in range(0, len(l), n)]

The leftrotate function is constructed as follows to perform the logical left shift operation:

def leftrotate(n, b):

return ((n << b) | (n >> (32 - b))) & 0xffffffff

A for loop operator is used to fill the array with 80 elements using a specific sequence of logical operations and perform transformations on the array elements.

The final result is obtained by sequentially writing the hash values. This process in Python is as follows:

result = '%08x%08x%08x%08x%08x' % (h0, h1, h2, h3, h4)

Output on the screen:

- Data = Samaqdand davlat universiteti
fefb6c45c424ae95d5e9bf697ed6c8dda820875e
Kirish hajmi = 29 bayt
Chiqish hajmi = 40 bayt
Amallarning bajarilish soni = 80*

SHA-224 (Secure Hash Algorithm 224) is a cryptographic hash function that belongs to the SHA-2 family^[2]. It is a shortened variant of the SHA-256 algorithm and generates a 224-bit hash value for the message. SHA-224 was developed by NIST in 2001 to enhance security and address the shortcomings of SHA-1. The SHA-224 algorithm generates a secure and immutable 224-bit hash value. It is used in digital signatures, certificates, and other security processes, especially in scenarios where storage space is limited.

SHA-256 (Secure Hash Algorithm 256) is also a cryptographic hash function belonging to the SHA-2 family and is one of the most widely used security algorithms^[2]. This algorithm processes input data and generates a 256-bit hash value. SHA-256 was developed by NIST in 2001 to improve security levels and enhance the SHA-1 algorithm. It is highly reliable for protecting information from tampering and

ensuring authentication. SHA-256 is commonly used in high-security domains, particularly in blockchain technologies like Bitcoin, and in encryption systems. Today, SHA-256 is considered reliable for security.

SHA-384 (Secure Hash Algorithm 384) is another cryptographic hash function in the SHA-2 family that generates a 384-bit hash value. SHA-384 was developed by NIST in 2001 for applications requiring high security. This algorithm is used in digital signatures, certificates, encryption, and other processes where long-term security is essential. SHA-384 is widely applied today in high-security systems and operations requiring long-term security.

SHA-512 (Secure Hash Algorithm 512) is also part of the SHA-2 family and is a cryptographic hash function with a high level of security. It produces a 512-bit hash value and is used in areas requiring a high level of security. SHA-512 was released by NIST in 2001. Its long hash value (512 bits) makes it resistant to collisions (two different pieces of data resulting in the same hash value), which contributes to its high security. SHA-512 remains one of the strongest hash functions in use today.

Results: The study of the SHA algorithm family reveals the advantages and disadvantages of the following SHA algorithms:

Algorithm	Length of hash value	Advantages	Disadvantages
SHA – 0	160 bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Simple algorithm; ➤ Efficiency; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Not resistant to collisions; ➤ Low security level; ➤ Rarely used today;
SHA – 1	160 bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Higher security level compared to the SHA-0 algorithm; ➤ Initially widely used in various security practices; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Vulnerable to collision attacks; ➤ Found to be inadequate against attacks in 2005; ➤ Does not meet modern security requirements;
SHA – 224	224 bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Shorter than the SHA-256 algorithm; ➤ Suitable for processes with limited resources; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 224-bit hash length may not be sufficient for applications requiring high security;

SHA – 256	256 bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ High level of security; ➤ Widely used in blockchain technology, significantly more reliable than the SHA-1 algorithm; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Long hash values can pose challenges for systems with limited resources;
SHA – 384	384 bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Offers the same security; algorithm as SHA-512 but with a reduced hash length; ➤ Well-suited for systems requiring high security; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Partially efficient compared to SHA-512; ➤ Not suitable for systems requiring 512-bit security;
SHA – 512	512 bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The highest level of security; ➤ Resistant to collisions; ➤ Efficient for large amounts of data; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hash length and processing require significant resources; ➤ Challenging for small-scale systems with limited resources;

This table outlines the specific advantages and disadvantages of each type of SHA algorithm. Generally, as the hash length increases, the level of security also rises, but this requires more resources and greater computational power. When choosing an algorithm, it is advisable to select the option that matches the system requirements.

Conclusion

The SHA (Secure Hash Algorithm) family plays a significant role in ensuring data security in cryptography. These algorithms are distinguished by their efficiency, security, and speed. The main versions of the SHA family are SHA-1, SHA-2 (SHA-224, SHA-256, SHA-384, SHA-512), and SHA-3, which differ in the following aspects:

Security level: SHA-1 is currently considered weak due to the discovery of collisions. SHA-2 algorithms are much more secure, but SHA-3 was developed to enhance security for the future.

Hash length: The length of the hash value varies across different versions (e.g., 256 bits for SHA-256, 512 bits for SHA-512), which impacts the level of data encryption.

Architecture: While SHA-1 and SHA-2 are built on the same principles, SHA-3 is based on a different mathematical model, making it more robust against various attacks.

Performance: SHA-2 remains widely used in practice, but SHA-3 can provide higher efficiency in certain cases.

In general, the choice among SHA algorithms depends on security requirements and operational efficiency. While SHA-2 is widely used today, the development of an even more optimal algorithm than SHA-2 is possible in the future.

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